

ASPECTS REGARDING THE MANAGERIAL, TECHNOLOGICAL AND ECONOMICAL EFFICIENCY OF THE THERMO-ENERGY SYSTEM IN ROMANIA POST PANDEMIC PERIOD

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Abstract

Purpose – The article aims to present an analysis on the possibilities of technological, economic and managerial efficiency of a thermo-energy system.

Methodology/approach – The research methodology adopted was based on the critical analysis of the existing situation in the field and the proposal of efficiency measures.

Findings – Ascertainment of the analysis highlighted the need for modernization works, including new investments, as well as the improvement of the management system.

Research limitations/implications – The limits of the research and the application of the analysis results are of a financial nature. Underfunding of the field limits the possibilities for modernization and efficiency.

Practical implications – The practical implications of the research takes into account the placing of the clients of the thermo-energetic system in the center of attention and the improvement of the necessary financing system.

Originality/value – The originality of the article is based on an extensive documentation, and based on it a critical analysis of the existing situation with proposals for efficiency measures.

Key words: management, thermo-energetic system.

Introduction

The national thermo-energetic system has a special importance both for the economic field (industry, agriculture, trade) and for the entire population. Consequently, the efficiency of this system must be a priority (Deonise and Ioana, 2022).

The District Heating Program was approved by Emergency Ordinance no. 53 of June 25, 2019 on the approval of the Multiannual Program for financing investments for modernization, rehabilitation, refurbishment and extension or the foundation of centralized heating systems of localities and for amending and supplementing the Law on community services of public utilities no. 51/2006, published in the Official Gazette no. 548 of July 3, 2019, Part I.

Production Management (MP), by definition, is the totality of activities of organization and management of the industrial enterprise, activities carried out in order to efficiently perform its main function, namely the production function, which represents the main object of activity of the industrial enterprise (Ioana, 2016).

Production management is more comprehensive than general enterprise management (GMM), in the sense that the activities related to production management are more numerous and comprehensive than those of GMM. In figure 1 we present the scheme of the definition of production management.

FIG. 1. Schematic representation of the definition of production management

1 - General Management of Enterprise (GMEs); 2 - Production Management (PM)

Obs. 1. A clear distinction must be made between the notion of function of the industrial enterprise (personnel function-human resource; financial-accounting function-financial resource; production function-material resource; commercial function; research-development-innovation-information resource function) and the notion of managerial function of the enterprise (forecast; organization; coordination; command; control).

Obs. 2. Production management activities must not end with the realization of P/W/S. It is very important to quantify (both quantitatively and qualitatively) the stage of sale of P/W/Ss produced and intended for sale. Thus, an own and real marketing study is implicitly carried out. Such a study can be carried out preferably through the Own Presentation and Sales Stores (MPPD), the so-called factory gates. The conclusions of this study represent mandatory and very useful needs for the new manufacturing program. In conclusion, tracking the sales of P/W/Ss produced must be a production management activity for a professional manager (craftsman).

Technical characteristics of basic energy equipment

The machinery and equipment specific to a thermal power plant are the following:

- the hot water boilers are monobloc type, made of steel in welded construction, with 3 distinct smoke roads and pressurized hearth;
- the boilers have the working parameters $P_n = 6$ bar and $T_t / T_r = 90 / 70^\circ\text{C}$ and the maximum combustion gas temperature at the exit is $\leq 185^\circ\text{C}$. Each boiler is equipped with a natural gas burner, modulating, with low emissions, electrical control panel, protection and signaling and with its own automation and protection installation. Depending on the thermal demand, the boilers come into operation in cascade, the thermal agent produced by the boilers being the primary agent for the heat exchangers;
- water circulation and recirculation pumps for each boiler;
- primary heat circulation pumps for heating heat exchanger;
- primary heat circulation pumps for a.c.c. heat exchanger;

- add-on water pump;
- the water softening station is an automatic two-column softening station equipped with ion exchange resins, which are alternatively regenerated, so as to allow the continuous supply of treated water;
- the expansion vessels are of closed type, with interchangeable rubber membrane, with capacity determined by the volume of water in the closed circuit installation.

The negative effects of the replacement of district heating installations in Romania

- The reasons that caused the disconnection (total or partial, with or without other sources of thermal energy supply) of an increasing number of apartments in the blocks of flats in Romania (about 800,000 out of a total of about 2,700,000) of to the centralized heat supply system are (Deonise and Ioana, 2022, Ioana, 2013, b, Ioana, 2012
- the increase in thermo-energetic tariffs, which determined the poor to give up any source of heating, and those with money chose as an alternative solution: to: pay less for maintenance costs, pay as much as they consume and have thermal comfort desired at any time of the year) installation of individual thermal devices (abbreviated as ITDs): "apartment microcentral" (AM), converters (C), supplied with natural gas, which evacuate the flue gases through horizontal chimneys (tubes) through the walls exterior of apartment buildings.
- The very aggressive advertisement of those interested in promoting ITDs, those who have presented only the advantages;
- deficiencies in the correct information of the population regarding the MULTIPLE NEGATIVE EFFECTS of the installation of ITDs in the blocks of flats;
- the lack of adequate measures of the decision-making forums regarding the PROTECTION of the entire population of Romania, because when some owners of a condominium install their ITDs (most often "apartment microcentrals" (AM) the negative effects are much amplified for the other co-owners to the central heating system;
- the ignorance by the Romanian authorities of the fact that the destruction of centralized heat supply installations is in contradiction with modern trends in the European Union.

LEGAL ASPECTS

The installation of ITDs by some owners without the consent of all co-owners of the condominium is an abuse, which violates the rights provided in the constitution of other owners

- Equal rights (art. 16 par. 1 and 2) "Citizens are equal before the law and public authorities without privileges and without discrimination"
- The right of property (art. 41) "Private property is equally guaranteed by law, regardless of the owner"; para. 6: "The property right forces you to respect the tasks regarding the protection of the environment and the assurance of the good neighborhood".

By evacuating the flue gas, the ITDs pollutes all the neighboring apartments, and the explosion of the ITDs or the gas supply installation can destroy the entire block.

That is why the installation of ITDs also endangers: the right to life, to the physical and mental integrity of the person (art. 22), the right to health care (art. 33), the protection of children and young people (art. 45).

The principle "I do what I want in my apartment" (as stated by those who install ITDs) can not be applied in a block in which through the initial construction the common facilities and the resistance structure (which includes the staircase and facade) is in the common property of all the co-owners of the condominium.

The realization of the gas installation for supplying ITDs on the staircase and the installation of AM or C with gas in the block apartments involves modifications of the common installations, of the staircase and of the facade), and maintaining the ITDs even without working, is a potential bomb "Which can explode at any time, leading to the destruction of the entire condominium.

The people who collaborate in the installation of ITDs with the evacuation of flue gases at the level where people take their breath, but especially the decision-making forums and the authorities with control functions of the Romanian state, which allow "gasification" of millions of citizens with burning of natural gas, could be considered complicit in human rights violations provided for in international documents. Art. 20 of the Romanian Constitution provides: "If there is a discrepancy between the pacts and treaties on fundamental human rights, to which Romania is a party, and domestic laws, international regulations have priority." Romania is a signatory of the Kyoto Agreement on limiting CO₂ emissions, being also a member of the European Union.

The European Union's Charter states the "Precautionary Principle": governments must base their regulatory policy on the significant possibility of risk, acting even before all data is collected.

The installation of these ITDs, by polluting the environment, contradicts the European legislation to which our country has adhered (Deonise et al, 2022).

Violated laws and other legislation

- Housing law no. 114/1996 with the subsequent amendments stipulates in art.14 of Annex 2: „, no owner can violate or prejudice the right of common or individual property.
- Law 10/1995 on quality in constructions, Art.5: „... c) fire safety; d) hygiene, human health, restoration and protection of the environment.”
- Law 453/2001 for the amendment and completion of Law 51/1991 on the authorization of the execution of construction works, provides in art.1: “The execution of construction works is allowed only on the basis of a construction authorization”, and in Art.3: „, The building permit is issued for: a) works of... .modification,... .or repair of constructions of any kind, as well as of the installations related to them”.

Pollution by natural gas and its combustion products in individual heaters

Methane, in the form of natural gas, was until recently considered the cleanest fuel for the production of heat and electricity, but recent studies have led to the identification in flue gases of at least 70 species, some major, some minor including aromatic hydrocarbons. substituted aromatic and polyaromatic (PAH) carcinogens at which there is no maximum permissible concentration.

Natural gas contains methane as the main component, but also other hydrocarbons, odorants contain sulfur, radon (radioactive), as well as a variety of impurities depending on the gas source (organometallic compounds, etc.). in addition, in ITDs natural gas is burned in the air, which contains as a major component nitrogen, which generates nitrogen oxides. Combustion of methane involves dozens of chemical reactions, many of them based on free radical mechanisms, inherently free radicals are generated by burning natural gas in the air.

By evacuating the flue gases in the ITDs through horizontal chimneys that penetrate the exterior walls of apartment buildings in Romania, directly in the vicinity of windows, balconies and other openings in the building envelope, all pollutants are brought to the breathing area of people living in those blocks. Therefore, the concentrations of pollutants in the exhaust gases (chimney) ITDs should not be compared with the emission limit values (such as if the flue gases were removed through chimneys above the roof level), but with the emission concentrations (ie with the concentrations of pollutants in the chimney). breathable air.

Discussion and conclusions

District heating companies have as field of activity the production, transport, distribution and supply of thermal energy, for the population and economic agents.

They manage the district thermal power plants, the thermal energy transmission networks, the thermo-energetic points and the distribution networks of the thermal agent to the consumers.

The current sources of thermal energy production are CHPs, area and district heating plants. Area thermal power plants have become sources of thermo-energetic production by transforming thermal points and thermal modules into thermal power plants. This situation has emerged as a necessity in some localities due to the cessation of activity at CHPs and the reduction of heat consumption due to

the massive disconnections from the centralized heat supply system on the one hand and the existing long transport distances, on the other hand.

The measures found and recommended to improve the efficiency of the entire district heating system are unitary measures that require investment costs for their realization and measures related to the daily operation of the installations.

Among the measures that require investment costs we note:

- Rehabilitation of primary and secondary thermo-energetic networks by replacing classic steel thermal pipes and insulated with mineral wool with pre-insulated pipe;
- Restoration of the metering system on networks, respectively restoration of the metering loops;
- Metering of all thermo-energetic points on all circuits: primary circuit input, heating utility and domestic hot water output, addition to the heating circuit, own and technological consumption at the thermal point level;

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